

STUDIES ON PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN BARGI DAM, JABALPUR

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ABSTRACT

The physicochemical parameters of Bargi Dam water, were studied during January to December 2006. The results revealed there was a significant seasonal variations in some physico-chemical parameters including water temperature, pH of water, suspended solids, total dissolved solid, chloride content, total hardness, dissolved oxygen, dissolved carbon dioxide, BOD, COD and sulphates. The parameters studied from the dam water shows the normal range and better quality.

KEYWORDS: Physico-Chemical Parameters, Water analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Water is important factor for the survival of living organisms. The quality of water and its resources depends on its physical, chemical and microbial characteristics. Assessment of water quality of the dam is an important aspects for the development activities of the region, because it is the sum of water supply of domestic, agriculture and aquacultural practices (Jain and Seetapathi, 1996; jakher and Rawat, 2003).

Limnology plays an important role in decision making process for the problems like dam construction, pollution control, fish and aquacultural practice (Muley and Gayakwad, 1999). The Deterioration of water quality, loss of biodiversity and fast depletion of water resources were the man challenges which need urgent attention. Changes in the water quality are reflected in the bitic community structure as shown by occurrence diversity and abundance pattern of species (Cairns 1997). The physico-chemical and biological characteristics of reverse and dam water were studied by kulkarni rajendra rao et.al. 2002; (Nisar Shaikh and Yeragi, 2004). In the present investigation water quality of Bargi Dam were studied in

order to assess its suitability for the mankind and agricultural use.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The water samples were collected monthly for the period of twelve months from Jan-Dec 2006 from Bargi Dam situated at 19°56' N latitude and 17°43' longitude. Temperature and pH were determine immediately while total dissolved solids suspended solids, chlorides, total hardness, dissolved oxygen, dissolved carbon dioxide BOD, COD, and sulphates and estimated in the laboratory by using standard methods of water (APHA 1992).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The water seasonal variation in physico-chemical parameters are given in Table-1.

Year	PH	Water Temp.	Suspended Solids	TDS	Chloride	Total Hardness	DO	Co2	BOD	COD	Sulph-ates
Jan.	6.8	22	11.5	26.6	32	48	3.1	10.9	2.7	2.6	4.7
Feb.	6.8	23	11.8	26.2	32	49	3.1	9.8	2.7	2.6	4.3
Mar.	6.9	25	11.9	24.0	32	53	3.0	9.4	2.8	2.7	4.0
Apr.	7.0	31	11.2	24.9	34	55	3.4	9.1	3.0	2.7	3.7
May.	7.1	35	12.5	25.0	34	59	3.9	8.5	2.9	2.8	3.1
June	7.0	34	11.4	28.0	34	58	4.1	6.9	2.8	2.6	5.0
July	7.0	32	15.7	29.6	29	53	3.7	5.9	2.5	2.5	5.3
Aug	6.9	29	16.5	31.0	28	45	3.5	7.0	2.4	2.2	5.6
Sept	6.9	30	17.0	31.1	27	46	3.3	7.5	2.3	2.0	5.5
Oct.	6.9	31	14.3	30.5	28	45	3.2	8.2	2.0	2.2	5.4
Nov	6.8	27	13.8	29.5	29	43	3.2	8.6	2.1	2.4	5.2
Dec.	6.8	21	11.8	27.5	30	44	3.1	9.7	2.5	2.5	4.9

Table-1:Physico-chemical parameters of Bargi Dam water, year January to December 2006.

1.All parameters are expressed in mg/l except pH and water temperature.

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In the present study the pH range was recoded 6.8 to 7.1. The high pH range was recorded in summer and lower in winter. The pH of water important for biotic components because most of the plant and animal species can survive and narrow range of pH slightly acidic to slightly alkaline condition. According to Reynolds et. Al.,

(1968) pH is considered to be the most important factor particularly in the case of green algae. The lower values of pH during rainy season may be due to dilution of alkaline substances or dissolution of atmospheric carbon-dioxide (Narain and chavan 2000). Anand and Sharma (2000) found the pH values in the range between 6.85 to 8.51 in mansard lake. Sheikh, Nisar and Yeragi (2004) recorded the pH from Tansa river, Thane.

The temperature of water were found to be in the range between 21° to 35°. The temperature of water was maximum in summer season and minimum in winter season. The temperature of water is an important physical parameter which directly influence some chemical reactions in aquatic ecosystem. The signification correlation between ambient temperature and water temperature was observed by Ganpati (1943 and 1962) and Verma (1967). Danillo (1963) pointed out the seasonal changes were mainly dependent on water temperature in Gidgich reservoir. The low oxygen values coincided with high temperature during the summer months (Mazhersultan and Dawwod Sharief 2004).

The total dissolved solid ranged from 240.5 mg/l to 310mg/l. The total suspended solid ranged from 11.5 to 15.7 mg/l. The high contents of total solids elevate the density of water and medium increases osmoregulatory stress on aquatic biota (Verma et. Al., 1978). The excessive total dissolved solids generally affects palatability. In river total dissolved solids increase is attributed to pollution by effluents (Mani Vasakam 1984). The highest record of water temperature coincided with annual maximum record of suspended solids, which absorb more heat in solution (Reed 1962, Reid and Wood 1976, Zutshi 1992, Jameson and Rana 1996). Khobragade Kshama (2003) observed the values of total solids from Akola city, Maharashtra. One of the important indicators of polluted water is chlorinity. The present results

indicated maximum chloride contents in the month of June (34 mg/l) and a minimum in the month of September (27 mg/l). Similar findings were recorded by Singh and Shrivastava (1988), Deshmukh and Lomte (1998).

The otal hardness ranged from 43mg/l to 59 mg/l. Mishra and Tripathi (2001) reported high value of 295 mg/l in Ganga river. Hiware and Jadhav (2001) found values of total hardness were 48.75 during summer and 34.5 mg/l during rainy season. The dissolved oxygen was varied from 3.05 to 4.1 mg/l during study. The dissolved oxygen was found to be maximum in the month of june and minimum in the month of March. Such seasonal observation has been confirmed by Khatavkar et. Al., (2004) and Khabade et. Al., (2002.) Skhare and Joshi (2003) Observed values of dissolved oxygen ranged from 2.03 to 7.08 mg/l.

High organic pollution indicates higher values of B.O.D. and C.O.D. were noted in the month of May (2.9 and 28 mg/l) respectively. It might be due to higher rate of decomposition and increase in temperature. Singh and Shrivastav (1988) found higher values of BOD and COD during summer due to high organic pollution and reduced flow of water. Sinha et.al., (1989) noted more BOD and COD values than the tolerance limits in Ganga river.

The sulphate indicates the pollution of water by domestic waste. In the present investigation the sulphate values weer maximum in the month of august (56 mg/l) and minimum in the month of May (31 mg/l). Similar findings were studied by Deshmukh and Lomte (1998).

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